

Extrinsic Inhibitory Control of Melanogenesis in the Post-melanosomal Era

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The concept of the melanosome as melanin polymer-forming site was a milestone in pigment cell science. However, this concept did not include an explanation of the site for melanin monomer-formation¹. In two-dimensional electron microscopy, using ordinary thin sections of dopa-reacted tissue, dopa melanin appears to be formed within a part of the Golgi apparatus and small intermediate vesicles as previously reported. However, by using a high voltage electron microscope with a goniometer to tilt the thick section of dopa-reacted tissue for 3-dimensional analysis, dopa melanin is seen distinctly forming in tubular, anastomosing and cisternal portions of Golgi associated endoplasmic reticulum of lysosome (GERL) and coated vesicles but not in the multi-layered sheet-structured Golgi apparatus and its outer element. The end-ports of these dopa-positive tubular and anastomosing GERL appear to be budding off to form strongly dopa-positive coated vesicles.

A biochemical analysis^{2,3} was made of these newly identified non-melanosomal melanogenic compartments after sub-cellular fractionation, in relation to the maturation and transfer of tyrosinase. On the basis of 3-dimensional electron microscopic and biochemical findings, our concept^{1,4} of melanogenesis was developed and is schematically shown in Fig. 1. This concept has lead us to control pigmentation more efficiently at the sub-cellular level. Based on these fundamental studies, and using etiologic analysis of melanocyte dysfunction, we could move towards the goal of clinically oriented dermatologic in-

vestigation, that is, to correct abnormal function through the development of new drugs tested by their in vitro/in vivo responses for pigmentation control.

Fig 1 The process of melanogenesis showing glycosylation of tyrosinase in the GERL and transfer of tyrosinase and melanin monomers by coated vesicles (C V) into pre-melanosomes

Glucosamine and its derivatives :

Tyrosinase synthesis occurs in the membrane bound polyribosomes of the rER and glycosylation of the enzyme is initiated in the endoplasmic reticulum shortly after synthesis. Further glycosylation and processing are carried out within the GERL. The glycosylated T3 is then transported from GERL to the pre-melanosomes by coated vesicles. On the basis of these findings we started to actively search for new glucosamine carbohydrate derivatives which could provide better suppressive control of melanogenesis with decreased toxicity. Thus, we synthesised many derivative compounds of glucosamine and examined

their depigmenting activity in relation to their chemical structure. Some of these derivatives, such as tetra-*O*-acetylglucosamine (TAG) exhibited considerably higher depigmenting activity than that of glucosamine. Some derivatives, such as 2-deoxyglucose and glucosamine HCl whose amino groups are modified at the second position, also exhibited depigmenting ability.

When $15 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ TAG was added to cultured B-16 cells, even in a concentration less than 2% of the concentration used in the glucosamine experiments, a depigmenting effect was obtained. When we examined changes in the tyrosinase isozymes in the depigmented cells, they showed a marked or almost complete loss of T_3 tyrosinase synthesis. Electron microscopy showed a complete interruption of melanin polymer formation in these TAG-treated cells. Again, depigmentation induced by this highly effective glucosamine derivative results from inhibition of melanogenically active T_3 tyrosinase.

Kojic acid :

Kojic acid [5-hydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-4-pyrone], which is present in bakers' yeast, is one of our recently discovered depigmenting agents. Kojic acid can strongly suppress the activity of isolated tyrosinase *in vitro* that can be recovered by the subsequent addition of copper acetate, indicating the role of binding action involved in kojic acid inhibition.

The addition of 2.5 mM kojic acid to cultured B-16 melanoma cells causes reversible depigmentation, shown as centrifuged pellets, as a result of the suppression and recovery of tyrosinase activity. An assay of these cultured pigment cells by Ito's method reveals the time course of parallel reduction and recovery not only of eumelanin but also of pheomelanin and its intermediate 5SCD during addition of kojic acid and after its removal. The reduction of melanin polymer content in cells treated with kojic acid compared to control cells is readily visible. When tyrosinase activity was checked by dopa reaction, there was a similar marked reduction in treated pigment cells, however,

in both cases, results indicate a preferred, moderate amount of inhibition and complete inhibition had not been obtained.

When we examine control and kojic acid-treated cells on the ultrastructural level, a marked reduction in melanin polymer containing melanosomes is apparent. Dopa reaction of the hyperpigmented control cells with parallel biochemical and cellular observation shows tyrosinase activity by the appearance of dopa melanin within subcellular compartments particularly in the GERL-coated vesicle system. A biochemical assay shows the reversible reduction of all tyrosinase isozymes T_1 , T_2 , T_3 along with their recovery. Kojic acid also markedly inhibits the conversion to 5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid from dopa-chrome suggesting possible inhibition of tautomerase activity⁴.

Fig. 2. The three points of kojic acid's inhibitory action.

As summarised schematically in Fig. 2, kojic acid has three points of action. First, it inhibits the enzymatic action of tyrosinase and this inhibition can be reversed by copper acetate. Second, conversion of dopa to 5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid is reduced, and third, kojic acid inhibits conversion of DHICA to eumelanin polymer. It should be stressed that even with these three action points, kojic acid has very little cytotoxic properties, and therefore can be called a reversible, functional melanogenesis-suppressive agent.

On the basis of these findings, we performed a series of double-blind tests using 45 volunteer subjects, on whose inside upper arm we applied

a 1% kojic acid containing cream and placebo cream to separate areas, along with uv irradiation. Kojic acid markedly inhibited uv-induced pigmentation compared to a placebo 21 days after application.

We have treated in my clinic a large number of patients with mostly epidermal hyperpigmentation disorders, mainly melasma, lentigo solaris and even lentigo senilis. After treatment with 1% kojic acid cream, melasma regresses considerably. Similarly, lentigo solaris and senilis treated with kojic acid could show marked regression. Visible improvement was observed 4 months after beginning applications for melasma and after 6 months of treatment, for lentigo solaris and lentigo senilis.

Pentadecenoic acid :

Among the many depigmenting agents which we have discovered, I will briefly discuss two more significant examples. The first example is pentadecenoic acid (PDA), a polyunsaturated fatty acid, which also shows a reversible depigmenting effect using B-16 cultured cell system. The complete loss of melanin polymer formation occurs in the well maintained structure of the premelanosomes after treatment with PDA, as compared to control. However, premelanosomes were miniaturised and their reactivity to the premelanosome reaction of Mishima was almost completely abolished.

In spite of almost complete loss of melanin polymer formation, when we perform electron microscopic dopa reaction, dopa-melanin can be induced in not only GERL and coated vesicle but also in most of the premelanosomes. These results suggest an entirely different mechanism of depigmentation as compared to the previous two examples. On the other hand, in tunicamycin and glucosamine induced depigmentation, a decrease in dopa melanin is only induced in GERL and coated vesicles but not in premelanosomes due to loss of T₃ tyrosinase. With kojic acid, moderate and incomplete inhibition of melanin polymer formation in premelanosomes

was obtained with marked decrease of dopa melanin in both GERL/coated vesicle and premelanosome systems. Biochemical analysis shown of PDA-induced depigmented cells, shows tyrosinase inhibition can be observed only for T₁ and T₂ isozymes, while T₃ levels are essentially maintained in accordance with observed electron microscopic dopa reaction.

Conclusion : As shown in the comparative summary in Table 1 of the three different modes of melanogenesis inhibition, glucosamine and tunicamycin inhibit the T₃ isozyme selectively by interruption of its glycosylation, and by preventing enzyme transfer from GERL to premelanosomes. On the other hand, kojic acid, because of its cooper binding action, enzyme inhibition generally occurs for all three isozymes. However with regard to PDA's depigmenting action, T₁ and T₂ activities are moderately suppressed, while T₃ activity is almost completely retained, in spite of complete inhibition of melanin polymer formation. PDA's mechanism of action is still under investigation, but so far, one possible explanation is that PDA can alter structural properties of premelanosomes and suppress peroxidase activities as well as increase protein kinase C activities. All of these actions are known to have some effect on melanisation properties.

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE SUMMARY OF THE THREE TYPES OF MELANOGENIC INHIBITION

Measured subject		Drugs*		
		PDA	KA	GN TN
Cell blackness		↓↓↓	↓↓	↓↓↓
Tyrosinase isozyme activity	T ₁	↓	↓↓	↑↑
	T ₂	↓	↓↓	→
	T ₃	→	↓↓	↓↓↓
Light microscope	non-dopa	↓↓↓	↓↓	↓↓↓
	dopa	↓	↓	→
	PMS	↓↓	→	↓↓↓
Electron microscope	non-dopa	↓↓↓	↓↓	↓↓↓
	dopa GERL	→	↓	↑
	CV		→	↓
	PMS		→	↓
	PMS reaction	↓↓↓	→	↓↓↓

*PDA = Pentadecenoic acid, KA = kojic acid, GN = glucosamine, TN = tunicamycin

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